

Homobinuclear Complexes of Magnesium and Calcium

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Magnesium and calcium are biologically important metals. A number of oxygen-bridged polynuclear complexes of magnesium and calcium have been reported¹. We have synthesised and characterised some mixed-ligand homobinuclear complexes of magnesium and calcium of general formula $[M_2L_2L^1]$, where M = Mg/Ca; L = deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol (ONP), salicylaldehyde (Sal H), salicylic acid (Sal A), anthranilic acid (anth) or 8-hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ); L^1 = deprotonated vanilidenebenzidine (Vanben).

Results and Discussion

The complexes have been found to be stable under dry condition. The analytical and physical data of compounds are recorded in Table 1. Analytical data suggest a 2 : 2 : 1 stoichiometry among metal, primary ligand and secondary ligand.

Infrared spectra of the Schiff base complexes has been studied². The $\nu_{CH=N}$ band has mostly been spotted at $\sim 1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Ir spectra of H₂Vanben showed two medium bands ($-CH=N$ -stretch) and in the spectra of the complexes these bands remain mostly undisturbed at 1630–1600 and 1600–1580 cm^{-1} , suggesting that the azomethine group is not involved in coordination. The OH group of H₂Vanben shows a broad medium band at 3360 cm^{-1} . The low position may be due to the involvement of OH group in hydrogen bonding. This band is absent in the spectra of the metal complexes suggesting deprotonation of OH group during complexation.

The sharp medium band at 1030 cm^{-1} (OCH₃) in the spectra of H₂Vanben has been spotted mostly at 1040 cm^{-1} except in case of $[Ca_2(ONP)_2L^1]$, in which it occurs at 1025 cm^{-1} . This shift of the band suggests involvement of OCH₃ group

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
				Mg/Ca	C	H	N
1.	H ₂ Vanben(=H ₂ L ¹)	Yellow	175	—	74.92 (74.33)	5.60 (5.30)	5.82 (6.19)
2.	[Mg ₂ (SalH) ₂ L ¹]	Deep yellow	280	6.24 (6.46)	68.16 (67.92)	4.67 (4.58)	3.45 (3.77)
3.	[Mg ₂ (salA) ₂ L ¹]	Light orange	285	6.08 (6.20)	66.22 (65.11)	4.72 (4.39)	3.54 (3.61)
4.	[Mg ₂ (8HQ) ₂ L ¹]	Dirty yellow	275	6.11 (6.09)	71.12 (70.05)	4.76 (4.56)	6.82 (7.98)
5.	[Ca ₂ (ONP) ₂ L ¹]	Brownish red	270	9.54 (9.90)	60.42 (59.40)	3.54 (3.96)	6.52 (6.93)
6.	[Ca ₂ (salH) ₂ L ¹]	Deep orange	275	10.12 (10.34)	64.81 (65.11)	4.88 (4.39)	3.74 (3.62)
7.	[Ca ₂ (salA) ₂ L ¹]	Grey	272	9.78 (9.92)	62.36 (62.53)	5.01 (4.21)	3.83 (3.47)
8.	[Ca ₂ (anth) ₂ L ¹]	Light brick red	280	9.37 (9.95)	63.05 (62.84)	5.25 (4.47)	6.38 (6.96)

in coordination. Charkraworty and Khanna³ also spotted ν_{OCH_3} in sodium vanillidene anthranillate at the same (1030 cm^{-1}) position. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band at 1290 cm^{-1} of the ligand undergoes a higher frequency shift by $20\text{--}40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes ($1310\text{--}1330 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggesting co-ordination of the ligand to the metal through the oxygen atom of the methoxy group. In case with the complex $[\text{Ca}_2(\text{ONP})_2\text{L}^1]$, the ν_{NO_2} band is observed at 1540 cm^{-1} , suggesting⁴ coordination through NO_2 group.

Experimental

Mg and Ca salts of different organic acids were prepared by reacting the metal hydroxide and organic acids in 1 : 2 mole ratio in acetone medium and were found to be of ML_2 composition by elemental analysis.

A mixture of vaniline (6.08 g) suspended in

methanol ($\sim 50 \text{ ml}$) and benzidine (3.08 g) was stirred for $\sim 1 \text{ h}$. The resulting yellow solid was washed with methanol and dried (100°). The mixed complexes were prepared by the general method of interaction of a suspension of magnesium or calcium salt of primary ligand in acetone with the secondary ligand, vanilidenebenzidine, in 2 : 1 mole ratio. The mixtures were refluxed with stirring on a hot-plate for 1 h and the resulting solids were washed with solvent and dried (100°).

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